

LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF IMAGES-SYMBOLS OF LITERARY TEXT

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***Abstract** – The article is devoted to the substantiation of a new approach to the interpretation of texts important for culture, namely, drawing attention to the images-symbols of the literary text, which are described in the linguoculturological aspect as units of the literary text that accumulate cultural text information.*

***Key words:** linguoculturological aspect, literary text, cultural text, image, symbol, figurative, symbolic, mythological, archetypal.*

Introduction. The image-symbol is considered as a concept inextricably linked with the artistry of the text, as a result of the joint creativity of the author of a work of art and the reader, when there is recognition, creation, formation, disclosure of the very conceptual essence of the image-symbol of the text through the simultaneous realization of the plans of its meaning - direct, figurative, symbolic, mythological, archetypal.

Main part. The examples given in the article really show that with the use of a special technique of lingo-cultural analysis of images-symbols, there is a "disclosure of the genetic memory of the individual" (Y. M. Lotman). Long and well-known poems are read with interest, the conceptually important words for people, connected with the universe, nature, and the person himself, become more visible and tangible, the hierarchy of the author's concepts is clearly defined, representing a historically significant section of a certain time. Therefore, it is so interesting to compare the pictures of the world of two poems of the same era and the revealed internal paradoxicality of the modern prose text.

Paying tribute to the author's theoretical erudition, considering all possible aspects for his research, we note that the revealed method of linguoculturological

analysis and the examples of the analysis of the classics and the present (A. Pushkin "Anchar", "Caucasus"; M. Y. Lermontov "From Goethe "; N. M. Kononov "Mikesha") more fully help to understand the true deep national and cultural meaning of the literary text and complement our aesthetic perception.

The article will be useful and interesting to everyone who is interested in the problems of the relationship and interaction of language and culture, to everyone who wants to reveal the secrets of the inner world of Russian writers and poets.

The gravitation towards syncretism of sciences and interdisciplinarity of concepts is a leading trend in the field of modern humanitarian knowledge. Being successive to the ideas of linguists B.A. Larin, L.V. Shcherba, P.M. Bitsilli and N.I. Tolstoy, the book is a comprehensive study of the regularities of the existence and functioning of the "third" culture and the corresponding vernacular linguoculture.

It can be stated without exaggeration that in Russian studies for the first time the reality of "folk", "elite" and other strata of culture is not simply postulated, but confirmed by the analysis of the representative corpus of oral and written texts, on the basis of which typical speech and behavioral practices and the system of value dominants, attitudes, principles are revealed, norms typical for carriers of vernacular speech culture.

Conclusion. Analysis of images allows us to identify the following associative connections formed by them. Thus, lingvocultural analysis of the characters made it possible to determine the absence of "negative" color actualization. Meaning of symbols and the expression of symbolic meanings: a creature with human-like, sometimes childish, friendly or aggressive (this is typical for a child) behavior; to have healing power; an expression of the motif of heaven and earth hierogamy. The results of the analysis show the special role of children's journalism in the process of upbringing and educating a child, which is determined by its pedagogical, moral and aesthetic potential. In short, the linguocultural analysis of symbols is very important in every field.

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